

A risk-averse location-protection problem under intentional facility disruptions: A modified hybrid decomposition algorithm.

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Abstract

The rising disruptions of interdictors force supply chains' designers to embody the protection decisions when locating the facilities. In the presence of variability in the intensity of disruptions, a risk measure is incorporated into the decision-making. The designer-interdictor bi-level problem, therefore, optimizes the joint location and protection decisions with respect to the conditional value-at-risk. This configuration has been absent from the literature. An accelerated modified Benders decomposition algorithm is developed and enhanced by being hybridized with a sample average approximation-based genetic algorithm. We examine how this new configuration influences the optimal solutions and assess the effectiveness of the proposed method.

Keywords: Facility location-protection problem, Conditional value-at-risk, Bi-level programming, Decomposition algorithm, Sample average approximation, Game theory.